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“MY LOVE, MY HEART”

Grabbing my pen and I knew, I'll write again about you
My love, my heart says it's you. This pen knows no bounds, your name became a new drug this pen knows
no bounds, my love you're all I want.

I am no artist but I'll paint,
I'll paint you with words as a flowery stains.
I'll start with your eyes. The eyes that never fails to amaze me when it reflects the light
Your eyes that will never look at me with the same passion as I am

Your lips, red as roses, passionate as sin,
I'll gave you my breath so you can live,
You're built of effort and you're the definition of perfection
How can i love someone so impossible as imagination?

Do you see me in the crowd? Do you see me cheering when you think there's so much doubt?
Do you see me laugh? When you joke and goof around? Do you see me wave my banner in the sea of
people Cheering?

Or do you notice my heart racing when you're dancing?

I love you for all that you are,
My heart races when I see from afar,
Your smile is million dollar fine
Your laugh is my favorite all the time.

Though you never know my name,
You're the only person I want to aim,
Though you never know I exist,
It doesn't matter, I love you endlessly.

